

HSbooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

High-level
recommendations for the
future standardisation
booster framework
contract

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HSbooster.eu – The essentials

- HSbooster.eu - Standardisation Booster for H2020 and HE Research Results
- Coordination & Support Action (101058391)
- April 2022 – September 2024
- Budget €2m
- HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-32 - Standardisation Booster for fostering exploitation of FP-funded research results
- Countries: Denmark, Spain, Italy, Ireland and Serbia

- Project Coordinator
- COMMpla Platform manager

- Automated services management

- EAG management
Open calls and EPE
management

- Training academy
management

- Proactive services
management

- Premium services
management

HSbooster.eu concept

European R&I projects get the chance to:

- Gain knowledge
- Meet standardisation experts
- Dive into relevant standards
- Analyze standardisation potential
- Develop a standardisation strategy

The impact of the Services & feedback

“We now have a clear idea of the impact that we could have on standards and the main standards we must consider. The service was interesting and will influence our project.”

“The experience with the service has been enriching and satisfactory.”

“We received great feedback... Beyond discussing approach and established engagements with SDOs, the expert advised us on how to create sustainable contributions with a so-called CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA).”

Structure & Content

Online material for self-learning

More than 20 modules

Webinars

Online training + game sessions

Onsite training + game sessions

[HSbooster.eu/training-academy](https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy)

Advanced:
Case studies
Use cases
Success stories
..

Intermediate:
How to find the right standard?
How to participate in TCs or WGs?
How are standards developed within international SDOs?
....

Beginner:
Why do researchers need standards and standardisation?
What is standardisation, and what are standards?
Who develops standards?
What are standard essential patents (SEP)?
.....

High-level Recommendations for the Future Standardisation Booster Framework Contract

- First draft: based exclusively on the learnings and experiences of the HSbooster.eu pilot project – available upon request
- Final Recommendations: will include results from a series of workshops with key stakeholders – available online in September.

7 key recommendations

1. Framework and Resources

2. Cooperation between key stakeholders

3. Premium Service

4. Tools and Services

5. Training Academy

6. Framework programmes and AUWP

7. Scaling

1. Framework and Resources

A future booster should **mature** the HSbooster.eu concept while maintaining a high service level. To do so, a clear scope and framework should be established, and sufficient **resources** allocated.

2. Cooperation between key stakeholders

Establishing a long-term, sustainable link between R&I and standardisation requires a tightly knit **cooperation** between key stakeholders. A future booster should promote interaction and cooperation between the booster, EC, the standardization communities, and beneficiaries.

3. Premium Service

The HSbooster.eu premium service concept has a proven track record of providing support and advice of a very high quality and with a high satisfaction score. A **continuation** of the premium service or a very similar concept is fundamental for a booster successor.

4. Tools and Services

HSbooster.eu has developed a comprehensive platform and a varied set of tools that can be pivotal in increasing the link between R&I and standardisation. The HSbooster platform and tools should be further **developed, promoted, and utilised** to reach their **full potential**.

5. Training Academy

Education and training are prerequisites for a successful and mutually beneficial relationship between R&I and standardisation. A future booster should **increase the use** of the existing Training Academy, add new elements continuously based on user **feedback and data tracking**, and be developed and advertised further to enhance usage.

6. Framework programmes and AUWP

Systematic integration of standardisation in framework programmes and full incorporation of standards/ standardisation in calls related to AUWP topics/items will strengthen **European priorities**. A closer link between R&I and standardisation requests should be established by linking relevant FP calls with AUWP topics and by collaboration with DG GROW and DG RTD to support European legislation and policy goals.

7. Scaling

Scaling and full implementation at member state level is paramount for a booster to create significant and longterm impact. Mechanisms for scaling should be developed in dialogue with **multipliers** and concepts for **one-to-many services** should be further explored.

Final Recommendations

- Final recommendations will be published in early September 2024
- Join us for the unveiling in Brussels:

Advancing Together: Impact through
Research, Innovation, and Standards
Expected date: 17th of September 2024.

Thanks

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